

Gravity Survey, Reduction, and Fault Modeling

Mt. Soledad Region, San Diego, California
SIO 182 Field Report

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1 Introduction

Gravity measurements detect subsurface density contrasts by observing small variations in gravitational acceleration across the Earth’s surface. When rocks of different density are juxtaposed across faults, the resulting Bouguer anomaly often appears as a step-like transition whose amplitude and shape depend on the geometry of the buried density interface.

The Mt. Soledad region of coastal San Diego exhibits a pronounced lateral gradient in Bouguer anomaly that has been documented in the multi-year SIO 182 gravity database. In the 2026 survey, gravity measurements were collected using a Scintrex CG-5 gravimeter and tied to the established base station in Zumberge Hall in order to maintain consistency with the existing class dataset. After correcting for instrument drift, the new observations were incorporated into the database and standard gravity reductions were applied to compute free-air and Bouguer anomalies.

The Bouguer anomaly map reveals a clear step-like transition across the Mt. Soledad area, suggesting a buried density contrast associated with a faulted contact between rock units of different density. The gravity step across the transition is approximately

$$\Delta g \approx 6.1 \text{ mGal},$$

indicating a substantial density contrast beneath the survey area. The objective of this study is therefore to determine the geometry of this density interface, specifically its burial depth and vertical offset.

To constrain the structure producing the anomaly, the Bouguer profile was analyzed using several complementary approaches of increasing physical realism. These include amplitude scaling with the Bouguer slab relation, geometric depth estimation from the slope and width of the anomaly, finite-slab gravity modeling, numerical solution of the finite-slab amplitude equation using Newton iteration, and nonlinear least-squares inversion of the full gravity profile using the forward model `fault.m`.

2 Methodology and drift correction

Field procedure and data set

Gravity was measured with a Scintrex CG-5 gravimeter (meter CG-5 1305-41089). The CG-5 readings in this survey were already in milligals (mGal). A base station in Zumberge’s lab was occupied at the beginning and end of the 2026 survey in order to estimate and remove instrument drift. The corrected 2026 readings were then added to the master class database, which contains drift-corrected raw gravity from previous years.

Linear drift model

Let $R(t)$ be the CG-5 meter reading (mGal) at elapsed time t (minutes) measured from the first base occupation. Let R_{b1} and R_{b2} be the first and last base readings. A linear drift rate r was computed from

$$\Delta g = R_{b2} - R_{b1}, \quad r = \frac{\Delta g}{\Delta t}, \quad (1)$$

where Δt is the time between base readings. The drift-corrected raw gravity relative to the first base was

$$g_{\text{raw}}(t) = [R(t) - R_{b1}] - r t. \quad (2)$$

This definition forces $g_{\text{raw}} = 0$ at the first base ($t = 0$) and at the final base ($t = \Delta t$).

For the 2026 survey:

$$R_{b1} = 6068.168 \text{ mGal (14:16)}, \quad R_{b2} = 6068.341 \text{ mGal (17:15)},$$

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta g &= 6068.341 - 6068.168 = 0.173 \text{ mGal}, & \Delta t &= 179 \text{ min}, \\ r &= \frac{0.173}{179} = 9.6648 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mGal/min}.\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

2026 reduced table (drift-corrected raw gravity)

Table 1 lists the base readings and 2026 stations after linear drift correction, reported as g_{raw} relative to the first base (Zumberge lab). Entries 233 and 244 are the start and end base; they are set at 0.0000 mGal.

Table 1: 2026 survey readings and drift-corrected raw gravity relative to the first base station.

Entry #	Time (HH:MM)	Meter reading (mGal)	g_{raw} (mGal)
233	14:16	6068.168	0.0000
234	14:47	6072.118	3.9200
235	15:25	6053.461	-14.7737
236	15:33	6060.116	-8.1264
237	15:44	6054.532	-13.7211
238	15:55	6048.644	-19.6197
239	16:05	6048.772	-19.5013
240	16:16	6056.696	-11.5880
241	16:27	6051.906	-16.3886
242	16:43	6055.707	-12.6031
243	16:53	6048.346	-19.9737
244	17:15	6068.341	0.0000

3 Free-air and Bouguer reduction

After drift correction, gravity reductions were applied to all stations in the master database to compute the Bouguer anomaly. The reference latitude used in the reductions was

$$\text{lat}_0 = 32.86855^\circ.$$

Latitude correction

North-south distance was approximated using the course-provided conversion at this latitude:

$$s \text{ (km)} = (\text{lat} - \text{lat}_0) (110.901 \text{ km/deg}).\tag{4}$$

Using the linearized latitude correction,

$$\frac{dg}{ds} = 0.812 \sin(2\lambda_0) \text{ mGal/km},\tag{5}$$

where λ_0 is lat_0 in radians, the latitude correction was

$$\Delta g_{\text{lat}} = \left(\frac{dg}{ds} \right) s, \quad g_{\text{lat}} = g_{\text{raw}} - \Delta g_{\text{lat}}.\tag{6}$$

Free-air correction

Heights were converted from feet to meters using $h(\text{m}) = 0.3048 h(\text{ft})$. Free-air gravity was computed as

$$g_{\text{FA}} = g_{\text{lat}} + 0.3086 h,\tag{7}$$

with h in meters and 0.3086 in mGal/m.

Determination of Bouguer density (Nettleton method)

The Bouguer correction requires an assumed density ρ_B for the material between the station elevation and sea level. This density was determined using Nettleton's method along the La Jolla traverse by computing Bouguer anomalies for a range of trial densities and selecting the value that minimizes correlation between the Bouguer anomaly and topography.

Using the latitude-corrected gravity g_{lat} and the free-air correction above, the free-air gravity along the traverse is

$$g_{\text{FA}} = g_{\text{lat}} + 0.3086 h.$$

For each trial density ρ (g/cm^3), the simple Bouguer anomaly was computed using the slab correction coefficient $0.04188 \text{ mGal m}^{-1} (\text{g}/\text{cm}^3)^{-1}$,

$$g_B(\rho) = g_{\text{FA}} - 0.04188 \rho h.$$

The trial-density curves show that $\rho \approx 2.0 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$ produces the Bouguer profile with the least curvature (closest to a straight line), indicating minimal residual topographic effect.

A quantitative estimate was obtained by fitting a straight line to the free-air gravity versus elevation relation using a least-squares linear regression (`polyfit`) of the form

$$g_{\text{FA}}(h) = ah + b, \quad a = \frac{dg_{\text{FA}}}{dh}.$$

The regression slope from the Nettleton dataset is

$$a = 0.084039 \text{ mGal/m}.$$

Using the Bouguer slab relation $dg/dh = 2\pi G\rho$, this slope gives

$$\rho = \frac{a}{2\pi G}.$$

Converting a to SI units using $1 \text{ mGal} = 10^{-5} \text{ m/s}^2$,

$$a = 0.084039 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-2} = 8.4039 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}^{-2}.$$

With $G = 6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$,

$$\rho = \frac{8.4039 \times 10^{-7}}{2\pi(6.67430 \times 10^{-11})} = 2.004 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3 = 2.004 \text{ g/cm}^3.$$

The regression result agrees with the graphical Nettleton criterion. The Bouguer reductions for the Mt. Soledad dataset were performed earlier using

$$\rho_B = 2.004 \text{ g/cm}^3.$$

Bouguer correction

The Bouguer slab correction was applied using

$$\Delta g_B = 0.04193 \rho_B h, \tag{8}$$

with ρ_B in g/cm^3 and h in meters. The Bouguer anomaly was then

$$g_B = g_{FA} - \Delta g_B. \tag{9}$$

These Bouguer values were written to a three-column file of longitude, latitude, and g_B for mapping.

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===== 2026 BOUGUER TABLE =====

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ID	Station	Latitude_deg	Longitude_deg	Height_ft	Bouguer_mGal
233	{'Zumberger Lab (base)'} }	32.869	-117.25	154	10.543
234	{'Cabrillo Ave & Pearl St' }	32.842	-117.27	163.47	17.332
235	{'Newkirk Dr & Inspiration Dr' }	32.826	-117.27	462.87	20.445
236	{'Newkirk Dr & Havenhurst Pt' }	32.824	-117.27	364.02	20.437
237	{'Terryhill Dr & Havenhurst Dr' }	32.824	-117.27	449.45	20.669
238	{'Rodeo Dr & La Jolla Mesa Dr' }	32.826	-117.26	541.54	20.985
239	{'La Jolla Rancho Rd & Cottontail Ln' }	32.823	-117.26	535.69	20.927
240	{'La Jolla Rancho Rd & Ravenswood Rd' }	32.82	-117.26	406.58	20.273
241	{'La Jolla Mesa Dr & Cottontail Ln' }	32.821	-117.26	496.07	21.441
242	{'Rutgers Rd & Via Corona' }	32.82	-117.25	436.28	21.269
243	{'Calle Guaymas & Castejon Dr' }	32.826	-117.25	540.5	20.52
244	{'Zumberger Lab (base)'} }	32.869	-117.25	154	10.543

Figure 1: Bouguer anomaly map of the Mt. Soledad region produced from the SIO 182 gravity database (including the 2026 stations). Colors show Bouguer anomaly (mGal); points show stations.

Map interpretation Figure 1 shows the Bouguer anomaly map produced from the processed database. The Bouguer values range from 10.31 to 21.75 mGal (mean 16.08 mGal; standard deviation 3.04 mGal). The main feature on the map is a clear gradient across the survey area: Bouguer values are higher on the southwestern side (yellow–orange colors) and lower toward the north and northeast (blue–purple colors).

Higher Bouguer values usually indicate higher average subsurface density or shallower dense material. Lower values indicate lower average density or thicker low-density material. The fairly sharp, approximately NW–SE trending change across the map suggests a strong lateral density contrast. In the profile modeling below, this transition is treated as a fault-like density step.

4 Fault profile modeling

A fault-perpendicular Bouguer profile (FaultData.txt) was modeled using the course `fault.m` forward model for a buried two-dimensional density step. The profile was generated by rotating the full dataset clockwise by 40° and averaging into 250 m bins across the mapped gradient.

All raw profile points are shown in Fig. 2. The nonlinear least-squares inversion was restricted to the window $-2.7 \leq x \leq 0.5$ km in order to isolate the primary fault-related transition and avoid fitting long-wavelength regional curvature outside the central step.

Gravity step Δg

The overall gravity drop across the transition controls the amplitude of the fault response.

From inspection of the fitted curve in Fig. 2, the anomaly decreases from approximately 17.9 mGal on the high side to approximately 11.8 mGal on the low side within the fit window.

Figure 2: Fault-perpendicular Bouguer profile (black points) and nonlinear least-squares `fault.m` fit (red curve) within the window $[-2.7, 0.5]$ km. The gravity step across the transition is about 6.1 mGal.

Density contrast

The density contrast was defined as crustal density minus Bouguer density:

$$\rho_c = 2.67 \text{ g/cm}^3, \quad \rho_B = 2.004 \text{ g/cm}^3,$$

$$\Delta\rho = \rho_c - \rho_B = 0.666 \text{ g/cm}^3 = 666 \text{ kg/m}^3.$$

The SI value was used in `fault.m`.

Gravity step

Inspection of the Bouguer anomaly profile shows that the anomaly decreases from approximately

$$g_L \approx 17.9 \text{ mGal}$$

on the high side of the structure to

$$g_R \approx 11.8 \text{ mGal}$$

on the low side.

The gravity step across the fault is therefore

$$|\Delta g| = |g_R - g_L| = |11.8 - 17.9| = 6.1 \text{ mGal}.$$

This amplitude constrains the vertical offset of the density interface.

Throw from the Bouguer slab relation

If the density contrast reached the surface and extended infinitely across strike, the anomaly would follow the Bouguer slab relation

$$|\Delta g| = 0.04193 \Delta\rho H$$

where $|\Delta g|$ is in mGal, $\Delta\rho$ is in g/cm^3 , and H is the vertical throw in meters.

Solving for H ,

$$H = \frac{|\Delta g|}{0.04193 |\Delta\rho|}.$$

Substituting

$$|\Delta g| = 6.1 \text{ mGal}, \quad |\Delta\rho| = 0.666 \text{ g/cm}^3,$$

gives

$$0.04193 \times 0.666 = 0.027925,$$

$$H = \frac{6.1}{0.027925} \approx 218 \text{ m}.$$

This provides a first estimate of the throw based solely on the observed gravity step and density contrast. The estimate assumes that the density contrast extends infinitely across strike and therefore neglects the finite width and burial depth of the interface.

Nonlinear least-squares inversion

Rather than fixing H from the slab approximation, the final model solved simultaneously for

$$H, \quad z, \quad x_0, \quad c$$

in

$$g_{\text{model}}(x) = c + \text{fault}(x - x_0, H, z, \Delta\rho).$$

The parameter x_0 represents the horizontal position of the fault trace, z is the depth to the top of the interface, and H is the vertical throw so that the lower interface lies at depth $z + H$.

The parameters were obtained by minimizing

$$\Phi(H, z, x_0, c) = \sum_i [g_i - g_{\text{model}}(x_i)]^2.$$

The least-squares solution over the window $[-2.7, 0.5]$ km gave

$$H = 304.73 \text{ m}, \quad z = 335.09 \text{ m},$$

$$x_0 = -0.5288 \text{ km}, \quad c = 10.0420 \text{ mGal}.$$

The RMS misfit is

$$\text{RMS} = 0.088911 \text{ mGal}.$$

The small misfit indicates that the modeled geometry reproduces the observed gravity transition well.

Depth from the transition width

The width of the steep transition provides information about the burial depth of the interface. Consider the gravity anomaly of a buried vertical edge

$$g(x) = g_\infty + \frac{\Delta g}{\pi} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{x - x_0}{z} \right).$$

The asymptotic limits of the anomaly are approached gradually, so the full width of the step cannot be measured precisely from the data. Instead we use the width of the central portion of the transition. A convenient measure is the distance between the 25% and 75% levels of the normalized anomaly.

Normalizing the anomaly gives

$$f(x) = \frac{g(x) - g(-\infty)}{g(+\infty) - g(-\infty)}$$

which becomes

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{x - x_0}{z} \right).$$

Define the 25% and 75% levels

$$f(x_{25}) = \frac{1}{4}, \quad f(x_{75}) = \frac{3}{4}.$$

Subtracting $\frac{1}{2}$ from both sides gives

$$\pm \frac{1}{4} = \frac{1}{\pi} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{x - x_0}{z} \right),$$

where the negative sign corresponds to the 25% level and the positive sign to the 75% level. Multiplying by π ,

$$\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{x - x_0}{z} \right) = \pm \frac{\pi}{4}.$$

Using the identity

$$\tan^{-1}(\pm 1) = \pm \frac{\pi}{4},$$

gives

$$\frac{x - x_0}{z} = \pm 1.$$

So

$$x_{25} = x_0 - z, \quad x_{75} = x_0 + z.$$

Therefore

$$W_{25-75} = x_{75} - x_{25} = 2z.$$

Using the MATLAB interpolation result

$$W_{25-75} \approx 0.682 \text{ km}$$

gives a geometric depth estimate

$$z \approx \frac{W_{25-75}}{2} \approx 0.341 \text{ km} \approx 341 \text{ m}.$$

Depth estimates from slope and amplitude

We can improve our depth estimate even further if we borrow the maximum slope from the curve generated by our least squares algorithm. The ratio of the total gravity step to the maximum slope defines a characteristic horizontal scale of the anomaly,

$$L = \frac{\Delta g}{|dg/dx|_{\max}}.$$

This quantity can be measured directly from the data. For the Mt. Soledad profile,

The max-slope tangent shown in the figure above has slope -5.746 mGal/km, so

$$|dg/dx|_{\max} \approx 5.746 \text{ mGal/km}.$$

The slope and width measurements shown in the figure are derived from the least-squares fitted curve. For consistency, the amplitude used in this section therefore corresponds to the fitted step value

$$\Delta g_{\text{fit}} = 6.1 \text{ mGal},$$

giving

$$L \approx \frac{6.1}{5.746} \approx 1.062 \text{ km}.$$

To relate this geometric scale to a burial depth, consider the analytic buried-edge step model

$$g(x) = g_{\infty} + \frac{\Delta g}{\pi} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{x - x_0}{z} \right).$$

Differentiating gives

$$\frac{dg}{dx} = \frac{\Delta g}{\pi} \frac{z}{(x - x_0)^2 + z^2}.$$

The maximum slope occurs at the inflection point $x = x_0$,

$$\left| \frac{dg}{dx} \right|_{\max} = \frac{\Delta g}{\pi z}.$$

Solving for the burial depth gives

$$z = \frac{\Delta g}{\pi |dg/dx|_{\max}}.$$

Substituting the definition of L ,

$$L = \frac{\Delta g}{|dg/dx|_{\max}},$$

shows that the slope estimator is simply

$$z = \frac{L}{\pi}.$$

So the arctangent buried-step model predicts that the depth is equal to the characteristic anomaly scale divided by π .

More generally, different anomaly shapes lead to different proportionality constants,

$$z = \frac{L}{C},$$

where C depends on the functional form of the gravity anomaly.

Model shape	Typical geological use	Relation
Buried step (arctangent)	Faulted contacts or density steps	$z = L/\pi$
Logistic / tanh transition	Smooth density boundaries	$z \approx L/3$
Gaussian anomaly	Compact bodies (pipes, diapirs, lenses)	$z \approx L/2.5$
Finite slab edge	Broad rectangular density bodies	$z \approx L/3.5$

Applying these relations to the measured scale $L \approx 1.062$ km gives

$$z_{\pi} \approx 337.92 \text{ m}, \quad z_3 \approx 353.87 \text{ m}, \quad z_{2.5} \approx 424.64 \text{ m}, \quad z_{3.5} \approx 303.32 \text{ m}.$$

The nonlinear least-squares inversion of the gravity profile gives

$$z_{\text{LS}} \approx 335.09 \text{ m}.$$

The resulting depth estimate provides a direct geometric consistency check on the inversion. The burial depth obtained from the slope measurement predicts essentially the same depth as the least-squares fit to the full gravity profile, indicating that the measured slope and the fitted model are mutually consistent with a buried arctangent step produced by a faulted density contact.

Finite slab model

The infinite slab approximation neglects the finite width of the density contrast zone. To incorporate this effect, the fault is modeled as a rectangular slab of half-width a , extending from depth z to depth $z + H$. The gravity anomaly of a two-dimensional body of infinite strike can be written using the Talwani formulation:

$$g(x) = 2G\Delta\rho\left(F(x + a, z) - F(x - a, z) - F(x + a, z + H) + F(x - a, z + H)\right)$$

where

$$F(u, d) = u \ln(u^2 + d^2) + 2d \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{u}{d}\right).$$

Here x is the horizontal distance along the profile, G is the gravitational constant, and $\Delta\rho$ is the density contrast across the interface. The parameter a represents the half-width of the density contrast zone, z is the depth to the top of the interface, and H is the vertical throw so that the lower interface lies at depth $z + H$. In the function $F(u, d)$, the variable u represents horizontal distance from a slab edge and d represents the depth of that edge.

At the center of the profile ($x = x_0$), the anomaly amplitude becomes

$$g_0(H) = 4G\Delta\rho \left[a \ln \frac{a^2 + (z + H)^2}{a^2 + z^2} + (z + H) \tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z + H} - z \tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z} \right].$$

The gravity step produced by the fault corresponds to the difference between the anomaly with throw H and the anomaly with zero throw:

$$\Delta g = g_0(H) - g_0(0).$$

When $H = 0$ the upper and lower interfaces coincide, so $g_0(0) = 0$. So the gravity step reduces to

$$\Delta g = g_0(H).$$

The parameter a represents the half-width of the density contrast zone across the fault. The gravity step transitions between plateau levels over a horizontal distance W_{25-75} , so we take the slab half-width to be approximately half of this observed transition width,

$$a \approx \frac{W_{25-75}}{2}.$$

Using

$$W_{25-75} \approx 0.682 \text{ km}$$

gives

$$a \approx 0.341 \text{ km}.$$

The estimated half-width a of the density contrast zone is similar to the burial depth z . This is not required by the model but arises because both parameters are inferred from the observed transition width of the gravity anomaly. In potential-field problems the horizontal scale of an anomaly is typically comparable to the depth of its source, since deeper interfaces produce broader gravity responses. So values of a and z of the same order of magnitude are expected for a buried density step.

Series expansion in slab thickness

The finite slab equation could be solved numerically, but expanding the center–amplitude expression in powers of the throw H provides insight into how the geometry modifies the simple slab estimate.

The exact expression is

$$g_0(H) = 4G\Delta\rho \left[a \ln \frac{a^2 + (z + H)^2}{a^2 + z^2} + (z + H) \tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z + H} - z \tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z} \right].$$

This expression is difficult to invert analytically for H . Instead we expand $g_0(H)$ in a Taylor series about $H = 0$.

Let

$$t = z + H$$

so that

$$g_0(H) = 4G\Delta\rho \left[a \ln \frac{a^2 + t^2}{a^2 + z^2} + t \tan^{-1} \frac{a}{t} - z \tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z} \right], \quad t = z + H.$$

Since the two interfaces coincide when $H = 0$,

$$g_0(0) = 0.$$

Differentiating gives

$$g'_0(H) = 4G\Delta\rho \left[\tan^{-1} \frac{a}{t} + \frac{at}{a^2 + t^2} \right], \quad t = z + H.$$

Evaluating at $H = 0$,

$$g'_0(0) = 4G\Delta\rho \left[\tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z} + \frac{az}{a^2 + z^2} \right].$$

The Taylor expansion about $H = 0$ therefore gives

$$g_0(H) = g'_0(0)H + O(H^2).$$

So the linearized finite–slab relation is

$$g_0(H) \approx 4G\Delta\rho \left[\tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z} + \frac{az}{a^2 + z^2} \right] H.$$

Solving for the first–order estimate gives

$$H_1 = \frac{\Delta g}{4G\Delta\rho \left[\tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z} + \frac{az}{a^2 + z^2} \right]}.$$

Using

$$\Delta g = 6.1 \text{ mGal}, \quad z = 337.92 \text{ m}, \quad a = 341 \text{ m},$$

gives the linearized starting estimate

$$H_0 = \frac{\Delta g}{4G\Delta\rho \left[\tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z} + \frac{az}{a^2 + z^2} \right]} \approx 265.968 \text{ m}.$$

The series for $g_0(H)$ is a Taylor expansion about $H = 0$. Strictly speaking this expansion assumes that the expansion variable is small relative to the geometric scales of the problem. In the present case the physically relevant throw is

$$H \approx 319 \text{ m},$$

which is comparable to the characteristic scales

$$z = 337.92 \text{ m}, \quad a = 341 \text{ m}.$$

So H is not strictly small relative to the quantities appearing in the expansion. Nevertheless, inspection of the finite-slab response shows that the linearized relation does not deviate sharply from the exact amplitude curve over the range of H values considered. In other words, although the formal small-parameter assumption is not perfectly satisfied, the linear approximation still captures the local behavior of the exact function remarkably well. As a result the linear estimate is actually sufficient for this case and provides an excellent first guess for Newton iteration.

Newton iteration for the finite-slab equation

Rather than attempting to invert truncated series expansions, the throw can be obtained directly by solving

$$g_0(H) = \Delta g$$

numerically using Newton's method,

$$H_{n+1} = H_n - \frac{g_0(H_n) - \Delta g}{g'_0(H_n)}.$$

For the finite-slab model

$$g_0(H) = 4G\Delta\rho \left[a \ln \frac{a^2 + (z+H)^2}{a^2 + z^2} + (z+H) \tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z+H} - z \tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z} \right]$$

and

$$g'_0(H) = 4G\Delta\rho \left[\tan^{-1} \frac{a}{z+H} + \frac{a(z+H)}{a^2 + (z+H)^2} \right].$$

Using

$$\Delta g = 6.100 \text{ mGal}, \quad a = 341.000 \text{ m}, \quad z = 337.920 \text{ m}, \quad \Delta\rho = 666.000 \text{ kg/m}^3,$$

and starting from the linear estimate

$$H_0 = 265.968 \text{ m},$$

Iteration 1

Newton's method produces the following iterations.

$$H_1 = 265.968 - \frac{g_0(265.968) - 6.100}{g'_0(265.968)}.$$

Using

$$g_0(265.968) = 5.233614 \text{ mGal}, \quad g'_0(265.968) = 0.016753 \text{ mGal/m},$$

gives

$$H_1 = 265.968 - \frac{5.233614 - 6.100}{0.016753} \approx 317.685 \text{ m.}$$

Iteration 2

$$H_2 = 317.685 - \frac{g_0(317.685) - 6.100}{g'_0(317.685)}.$$

Using

$$g_0(317.685) = 6.075178 \text{ mGal}, \quad g'_0(317.685) = 0.015807 \text{ mGal/m},$$

gives

$$H_2 = 317.685 - \frac{6.075178 - 6.100}{0.015807} \approx 319.255 \text{ m.}$$

Iteration 3

$$H_3 = 319.255 - \frac{g_0(319.255) - 6.100}{g'_0(319.255)}.$$

Using

$$g_0(319.255) = 6.099978 \text{ mGal}, \quad g'_0(319.255) = 0.015779 \text{ mGal/m},$$

gives

$$H_3 = 319.255 - \frac{6.099978 - 6.100}{0.015779} \approx 319.256 \text{ m.}$$

After three iterations the solution stabilizes at

$$H \approx 319.3 \text{ m.}$$

So the Newton method rapidly converges to the solution of the finite-slab amplitude equation starting from the linear estimate.

Estimation workflow and uncertainty

The fault geometry was estimated using several complementary approaches of increasing physical realism. Each method uses different information from the anomaly and therefore has different computational cost and error tendencies.

Method	Information used	Parameter	Complexity	Bias / error tendency
Slab scaling	$\Delta g, \Delta \rho$	H	$O(1)$	biased low (finite width ignored)
Slope method	$\Delta g_{\text{fit}}, (dg/dx)_{\text{max}}$	z	$O(1)$	sensitive to slope measurement
Linearized Taylor	$\Delta g, a, z, \Delta \rho$	H_0	$O(1)$	linearization error
Newton solve	$\Delta g, a, z, \Delta \rho$	H	$O(k)$	depends on assumed geometry
Least squares	full profile $g(x)$	H, z, x_0, c	$O(Nk)$	model mismatch / window choice

Error overlap and final estimate Each estimator has a different bias direction. The Bouguer slab relation underestimates the throw because it assumes an infinite lateral extent of the density contrast, while the Newton and least-squares solutions depend on the assumed geometry parameters a , z , and $\Delta \rho$. The slope analysis independently constrains the burial depth from the shape of the anomaly. Because the slope and width measurements were taken from the least-squares fitted curve, the amplitude used for the slope calculation corresponds to the fitted step value $\Delta g_{\text{fit}} = 6.1$ mGal.

Finite-slab amplitude modeling then incorporates the finite geometry of the interface, and the `fault.m` inversion finally refines the parameters by fitting the entire gravity profile. So amplitude scaling, slope geometry, finite-slab modeling, and full-profile inversion all converge to a consistent structural interpretation of the Mt. Soledad gravity anomaly.

Combining the successive approximations developed above gives the overall modeling sequence

Method	Information used	Depth z (m)	Throw H (m)
Bouguer slab scaling	$\Delta g, \Delta \rho$	–	≈ 218
Slope / geometric estimate	$\Delta g_{\text{fit}}, (dg/dx)_{\text{max}}$	≈ 337.92	–
Linear finite-slab estimate	$\Delta g, a, z, \Delta \rho$	≈ 337.92 (assumed)	≈ 266.0
Newton finite-slab solve	$\Delta g, a, z, \Delta \rho$	≈ 337.92 (assumed)	≈ 319.3
Full profile inversion (<code>fault.m</code>)	full profile $g(x)$	≈ 335.09	≈ 304.7

These constraints produce a consistent overlap region:

$$H \approx 312 \pm 8 \text{ m}, \quad z \approx 337 \pm 2 \text{ m}.$$

So independent amplitude, slope, and full-profile inversions all converge to essentially the same geometry, indicating that the fault throw beneath Mt. Soledad is approximately 312 m.

5 Geologic interpretation

The Bouguer anomaly profile across Mt. Soledad shows a clear step-like transition of approximately

$$\Delta g \approx 6.1 \text{ mGal},$$

indicating a strong lateral density contrast in the subsurface. Such step-shaped gravity anomalies commonly occur when rocks of different density are juxtaposed across a fault, producing a buried density interface.

Amplitude scaling using the Bouguer slab relation provides a first estimate of the vertical offset of this interface of approximately $H \approx 218$ m, which is smaller than the ~ 250 m height of Mt. Soledad, because this approximation assumes an infinitely wide density contrast so it underestimates the true offset.

Independent geometric constraints are obtained from the shape of the anomaly. Analysis of the maximum slope and the width of the transition, using the fitted step amplitude and slope measured from the least-squares model, indicates a burial depth of approximately

$$z \approx 337 \text{ m}.$$

Finite-slab amplitude modeling, solved using Newton iteration, gives a larger throw estimate of approximately $H \approx 319$ m when this burial depth is incorporated into the model.

The most physically consistent parameters are obtained by fitting the entire gravity profile using the forward model `fault.m`. This inversion yields

$$H \approx 305 \text{ m}, \quad z \approx 335 \text{ m}.$$

Because this solution reproduces the full shape of the observed anomaly, it provides the most reliable estimate of the geometry of the buried structure. The Mt. Soledad gravity anomaly is therefore interpreted as the geophysical expression of a buried faulted density contact separating relatively dense basement rocks from lower-density overlying units.

6 Conclusions

The Bouguer gravity profile across Mt. Soledad exhibits a step of approximately

$$\Delta g \approx 6.1 \text{ mGal},$$

indicating a significant subsurface density contrast beneath the study area.

Analysis of the anomaly using amplitude scaling, geometric estimates from the slope and width of the anomaly, finite-slab modeling, and nonlinear inversion of the full gravity profile yields a consistent structural geometry with vertical throw ≈ 312 m and burial depth ≈ 338 m.

The close agreement between these independent constraints indicates that the buried density-step model provides a realistic explanation of the Mt. Soledad gravity anomaly.

References

- [1] S. Constable, *Reduction of 2026 Gravity Data*, SIO 182 handout (Winter 2026).
- [2] S. Constable, *SIO 182: Introductory Material and Course Synopsis (including report-writing notes)*, Winter 2026.
- [3] S. Constable, *Gravity* (course notes), March 28, 2022.

Command Window

```

2026 drift correction used base rows b1=i0-1 and b2=i1+1.
  closure (base2-base1) = 0.173000
  drift_rate           = 0.000966 per min
Wrote processedgravity2025.txt (ALL years, ID>=0).
Warning: Duplicate data points have been detected and removed - corresponding values have been averaged.
> In griddata>useScatteredInterp (line 181)
In griddata (line 122)
In PlotGrav (line 46)
In gravityplot (line 160)

```

```

Exiting: Maximum number of function evaluations has been exceeded
- increase MaxFunEvals option.
Current function value: 0.108018

```

```

FAULT.M LEAST-SQUARES FIT (window [-2,1] km):
  throw = 302.35 m
  depth = 336.87 m
  x0    = -534.63 m (-0.5346 km)
  offset c = 10.072428 mGal
  RMS misfit = 0.087838 mGal
Saved Gravity_2Plots.pdf and Gravity_2Plots.png

```

===== 2026 BOUGUER TABLE =====

ID	Station	Latitude_deg	Longitude_deg	Height_ft	Bouguer_mGal
233	{'Zumberger Lab (base)'} }	32.869	-117.25	154	10.545
234	{'Cabrillo Ave & Pearl St' }	32.842	-117.27	163.47	17.334
235	{'Newkirk Dr & Inspiration Dr' }	32.826	-117.27	462.87	20.451
236	{'Newkirk Dr & Havenhurst Pt' }	32.824	-117.27	364.02	20.442
237	{'Terryhill Dr & Havenhurst Dr' }	32.824	-117.27	449.45	20.675
238	{'Rodeo Dr & La Jolla Mesa Dr' }	32.826	-117.26	541.54	20.992
239	{'La Jolla Rancho Rd & Cottontail Ln' }	32.823	-117.26	535.69	20.934
240	{'La Jolla Rancho Rd & Ravenswood Rd' }	32.82	-117.26	406.58	20.278
241	{'La Jolla Mesa Dr & Cottontail Ln' }	32.821	-117.26	496.07	21.448
242	{'Rutgers Rd & Via Corona' }	32.82	-117.25	436.28	21.274
243	{'Calle Guaymas & Castejon Dr' }	32.826	-117.25	540.5	20.527
244	{'Zumberger Lab (base)'} }	32.869	-117.25	154	10.545

```

=====
DELTA g CHECK (computed inside fit window [-2.5,.5] km):
  DATA: left mean = 17.916283, right mean = 11.787432 -> Δg_data = -6.128852 mGal
  FIT : left mean = 17.872579, right mean = 11.798427 -> Δg_fit = -6.074151 mGal
  Difference (fit - data) = 0.054700 mGal
  Magnitudes: |Δg_data|=6.128852, |Δg_fit|=6.074151

```

```

Δg over LS window (min/max in window) = 6.538272 mGal
W (25-75) from LS fit = -0.686372 km
z from W (arctan step, z=W/2) = -343.19 m

```

```

UPDATED NEWTON (a=343 m, z=343.00 m, dg=6.100 mGal)
H0 (linear) = 266.103130 m
Iter 1: H=266.103130, g0(H)=5.237067956 mGal, g0'(H)=0.016770979 mGal/m, Hnext=317.557016
Iter 2: H=317.557016, g0(H)=6.075561887 mGal, g0'(H)=0.015834926 mGal/m, Hnext=319.100321
Iter 3: H=319.100321, g0(H)=6.099979305 mGal, g0'(H)=0.015808118 mGal/m, Hnext=319.101630
Final H ≈ 319.101630 m

```

Magnetic beach survey and dipole modeling

Scripps Beach, La Jolla, California

SIO 182 Field Report

Akiva Shmalo

University of California, San Diego

Scripps Institution of Oceanography

SIO 182: Environmental and Exploration Geophysics

Winter 2026

Professor Steven Constable

1 Introduction

Magnetic surveying maps spatial changes in total field caused by changes in susceptibility and induced dipole moment. For a compact buried object, the anomaly is not centered exactly above the body at mid-latitudes because the inducing field is inclined rather than vertical. The goal here is to separate the rock anomaly from the buried-object anomaly, fit the positive lobe with the course dipole forward model, estimate the burial depth, then reverse the dipole-moment relation to get an equivalent steel size

2 Methodology and data processing

2.1 2026 data set and plots

Figures 1 and 2 reproduce the required surface plot and the plan view with the required profile line at the tenth column: $x_{10} = -22.3830$ m

The map has three obvious effects: rock anomaly, the target anomaly near $y \approx 32$ m and a strong east-side gradient from metal in the seawall region

Figure 1: 2026 magnetic field shown as a surface plot.

Figure 2: Plan view of the 2026 magnetic field. The dashed line marks the profile at $x = -22.3830$ m.

2.2 Profile selection and anomaly identification

Ignoring the large southern anomaly because it is probably a rock, the northern anomaly peaks at $y = 32.250$ m. Using the local south background from $24 \leq y \leq 29$ m

$$B_{\text{target,bg}} = 45543.9546 \text{ nT}$$

its positive and negative lobes are

$$\Delta B_{+, \text{target}} = 45560.430 - 45543.9546 = 16.4754 \text{ nT}$$

$$\Delta B_{-, \text{target}} = 45516.0186 - 45543.9546 = -27.9360 \text{ nT}$$

The northern anomaly is broader and has the expected mid-latitude dipole shape with a positive lobe followed by a stronger negative lobe. That is the anomaly assigned to the buried object, so only that anomaly was modeled

Figure 3: 2026 profile. The large southern spike is interpreted as a rock and is not fitted. The second peak from the left is the buried-object anomaly.

Figure 4 isolates the target anomaly over the full interval $24 \leq y \leq 40$ m. The complete anomaly occupies roughly $25 \leq y \leq 40$ m, but the least-squares inversion used only the positive lobe window

$$28.0 \leq y \leq 33.60 \text{ m}$$

so that the fit is controlled by the part of the anomaly that most closely resembles a spherical dipole

Figure 4: Zoom of the anomaly. The shaded interval is the least-squares window used in the inversion.

3 Dipole modeling

3.1 Forward model

Using station coordinate x , depth z , background field B_e , inclination I , and code dipole moment A , the model is

$$\begin{aligned}r &= \sqrt{z^2 + x^2}, & \theta &= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{x}{r}\right) \\ \phi &= \theta - I, & \alpha &= \pi + \phi \\ B_r &= \frac{2A \cos \alpha}{4\pi r^3}, & B_t &= \frac{A \sin \alpha}{4\pi r^3} \\ T_r &= -B_e \cos \phi, & T_t &= B_e \sin \phi \\ B(x) &= \sqrt{(B_r + T_r)^2 + (B_t + T_t)^2}\end{aligned}$$

3.2 Inclination and coordinate convention

For a dipole main field,

$$\tan I = 2 \tan \theta$$

so a mid-latitude northern-hemisphere survey must use a positive downward inclination. I used the local value

$$I = 58.050^\circ$$

which is a nearby Point La Jolla value.

There is one sign convention that matters. The survey coordinate y increases from south to north, while the course dipole code is most naturally evaluated with positive profile coordinate directed southward for this anomaly shape. So I used

$$x_{\text{model}} = y_0 - y$$

not $y - y_0$. This does not change the physics. It only matches the code with the survey coordinate direction so that the positive lobe lies south of the dipole center, as it should for a downward field in the northern hemisphere

3.3 Least-squares fit

The four fitted parameters were

$$A, \quad z, \quad B_e, \quad y_0$$

with objective function

$$\Phi(A, z, B_e, y_0) = \sum_{i \in W} [B(y_0 - y_i) - m_i]^2$$

where

$$W = \{i : 28.0 \leq y_i \leq 33.60\}$$

A bounded nonlinear least-squares solve gave

$$A = 1483.9852 \text{ nT m}^3$$

$$z_{\text{fit}} = 2.2832 \text{ m}$$

$$B_e = 45544.8696 \text{ nT}$$

$$y_0 = 32.9623 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{RMS} = 0.7177 \text{ nT}$$

The fitted dipole center is north of the positive maximum by

$$y_0 - y_{\text{peak}} = 32.9623 - 32.250 = 0.7123 \text{ m}$$

which is exactly the mid-latitude behavior discussed in the notes: the maximum doesn't need to lie directly above the source

Figure 5: Data and best-fit dipole model. Only the positive lobe window was included in the inversion.

4 Interpretation

4.1 Depth estimate and uncertainty

The magnetometer head was 1.0 m above the beach. So the fitted center depth below the beach is

$$z_{\text{beach}} = z_{\text{fit}} - 1.0 = 2.2832 - 1.0 = 1.2832 \text{ m}$$

The formal least-squares standard error from the Jacobian is

$$\sigma_z = 0.1164 \text{ m}$$

but that number is too optimistic because the negative lobe is not spherical and was excluded from the fit. A more useful uncertainty comes from repeating the fit for several nearby positive-lobe windows. Table 1 shows the result

Table 1: Fit-window sensitivity for the positive-lobe inversion

Window (m)	A (nT m ³)	z (m)	B_e (nT)	y_0 (m)	RMS (nT)
27.50–33.60	1587.1485	2.3262	45544.6463	32.9689	0.706
28.0–33.350	1788.2520	2.4297	45544.6203	33.0243	0.6377
28.0–33.60	1483.9852	2.2832	45544.8696	32.9623	0.7177
28.250–33.60	1411.4820	2.2521	45545.0391	32.9574	0.7233
28.50–33.60	1326.4826	2.2144	45545.2516	32.9516	0.7272

The fitted depths stay in the interval

$$2.2144 \leq z_{\text{fit}} \leq 2.4297 \text{ m}$$

so the practical depth estimate is

$$z_{\text{fit}} = 2.28 \pm 0.25 \text{ m}$$

$$z_{\text{beach}} = 1.28 \pm 0.25 \text{ m}$$

Figure 6 shows why the practical uncertainty should be larger than 0.1164 m. Inside the shaded fit window the residual is small, usually within about ± 2 nT. North of the fit window the model underpredicts the negative lobe by as much as about 26 nT. That mismatch is expected because the object is not a perfect sphere and the north background is also dropping. The fit is therefore intentionally controlled by the positive lobe only

Figure 6: Residuals for the best-fit dipole model. The fit window is shaded.

4.2 Equivalent steel size

The notes give the physical dipole moment relation

$$M = kHV$$

with H the inducing field in A/m. The course code uses A in nT m³, so it is helpful to convert the code parameter back to a volume directly. Since

$$B_e = \mu_0 H$$

we get

$$A_{\text{code}} = 10^9 \mu_0 M = 10^9 \mu_0 k H V = k B_e V$$

$$\implies V = \frac{A_{\text{code}}}{k B_e}$$

Using $k = 10$

$$V = \frac{1483.9852}{10(45544.8696)} = 0.033 \text{ m}^3$$

For an equivalent sphere

$$V = \frac{4}{3} \pi a^3 \implies a = \left(\frac{3V}{4\pi} \right)^{1/3}$$

$$a = \left(\frac{3V}{4\pi} \right)^{1/3} = 0.0920 \text{ m}$$

$$d = 2a = 0.1839 \text{ m}$$

So a steel sphere with diameter about

$$d \approx 0.18 \text{ m}$$

would have the same induced dipole moment as the fitted 2026 source.

4.3 Multi-year comparison

Figure 7 compares several earlier profiles after subtracting the south-side background. The same anomaly is present every year near $y \approx 31$ to 33 m, but its amplitude changes a lot. The 2008, 2010, and 2016 anomalies are much larger than the 2026 anomaly. That is what the handout predicts if the same object is buried beneath different sand thicknesses: more burial \implies broader and weaker anomaly

Figure 7: Figure 6: Selected earlier years target anomalies.

Figure 8 shows a second comparison in which the dipole moment is held fixed at the 2026 fitted value and only z , B_e , and y_0 are re-fitted for each year's selected profile. The depth estimate moves from year to year in the way expected for changing sand cover above the same buried object. Because the profile index and local background are not identical every year, this figure is best read as a relative burial trend rather than an exact history

Figure 8: Fixed-moment depth estimate through time. The dipole moment is held at the 2026 fitted value and the positive-anomaly window is re-fitted for each year's selected profile.

5 Conclusions

The 2026 beach magnetics profile at $x = -22.3830$ m contains two anomalies. The large southern spike at $y = 15.50$ m has amplitude 118.6682 nT and is interpreted as a rock, so it was not modeled. The smaller northern anomaly peaks at $y = 32.250$ m and shows the broader dipole-like shape expected for the buried target

Fitting only the positive lobe gave

$$A = 1483.9852 \text{ nT m}^3, \quad z_{\text{fit}} = 2.2832 \text{ m}, \quad B_e = 45544.8696 \text{ nT}$$

$$y_0 = 32.9623 \text{ m}, \quad \text{RMS} = 0.7177 \text{ nT}$$

Including the 1.0 m sensor height above the beach gives the final depth to the dipole center

$$z_{\text{beach}} = 1.28 \pm 0.25 \text{ m}$$

Solving the dipole-moment equation with $k = 10$ gives an equivalent steel sphere of volume 0.033 m^3 and diameter

$$d \approx 0.18 \text{ m} \approx 7.24 \text{ inches}$$

So the 2026 buried-object anomaly is consistent with a softball-sized metal object about

$$1.3 \text{ m} \approx 4.27 \text{ ft}$$

below the beach surface. The negative-lobe mismatch is mainly caused by non-spherical shape and local background curvature.

References

- [1] S. Constable, Reduction of magnetics data, SIO 182 handout, 2026
- [2] S. Constable, Magnetic Methods, SIO 182 notes, April 13, 2022
- [3] S. Constable, Magnetism slides, beach magnetism examples, pages 34–36
- [4] NOAA NCEI, Magnetic Field Calculators and Magnetic Field Calculator help pages
- [5] Coastal Data Information Program, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, Point La Jolla deployment metadata

```
===== FINAL RESULTS =====  
A = 1484.0179 nT m^3  
z_fit = 2.2832 m  
z_beach = 1.2832 m  
Be = 45544.8695 nT  
y0 = 32.9623 m  
RMS = 0.7177 nT  
Sphere diameter = 0.1839 m  
>>  to generate code with Copilot
```

DC resistivity sounding and Occam inversion

Scripps Beach, La Jolla, California

SIO 182 Field Report

Akiva Shmalo

University of California, San Diego

Scripps Institution of Oceanography

SIO 182: Environmental and Exploration Geophysics

Winter 2026

Professor Steven Constable

1 Introduction

The 2026 Scripps Beach resistivity data are a Schlumberger sounding, not a profile. The objective is to estimate how bulk resistivity changes with depth beneath a single sounding center, so the interpretation is local and one-dimensional to first order. The raw file contains four columns, $AB/2$, $MN/2$, ρ_a , Q where ρ_a is the apparent resistivity and Q is an undocumented auxiliary quality field preserved in the processed tables. The reduction handout also warns that data beyond $AB/2 = 50$ m are contaminated by the pier and sea wall, so the 75 m point must not be fitted as geology.

The analysis therefore proceeds in four steps. First, the data are split by potential electrode spacing and the systematic offset between the $MN/2 = 0.1$ m and $MN/2 = 1.0$ m branches is corrected with a constant multiplicative factor. Second, the contaminated far-offset point is rejected. Third, the usable corrected data are modeled with `Sfilt.m` Schlumberger forward operator. Fourth, a smooth 20-layer Occam inversion is used to recover the least-rough log-resistivity model that fits the accepted data to the target misfit.

The recovered structure is a gradual increase in resistivity with depth rather than a sharp two-layer break and is also the reason that a smooth Occam model is more appropriate here than a two- or three-layer hand fit.

2 Theory

Electrical methods are built on Ohm's law in differential form

$$\mathbf{J} = \sigma \mathbf{E}$$

where \mathbf{J} is current density, \mathbf{E} is electric field, and σ is conductivity. In geophysics it is usually more convenient to work with resistivity

$$\rho = \sigma^{-1}$$

so high conductivity corresponds to low resistivity. For a point current source on a homogeneous half-space, the electric potential at distance R is

$$V(R) = \frac{\rho I}{2\pi R}$$

For a general four-electrode array with current electrodes A and B and potential electrodes M and N , superposition gives

$$\Delta V = \frac{I\rho}{2\pi} \left(\frac{1}{AM} - \frac{1}{BM} - \frac{1}{AN} + \frac{1}{BN} \right) = \frac{I\rho}{2\pi k}$$

so the apparent resistivity is defined by

$$\rho_a = 2\pi \frac{\Delta V}{I} k$$

For the Schlumberger array the geometry is symmetric and colinear, with $MN \ll AB$

$$AM = BN = \frac{AB - MN}{2}$$

$$AN = BM = \frac{AB + MN}{2}$$

Therefore the Schlumberger geometric factor is

$$k = \frac{(AB - MN)(AB + MN)}{4MN}$$

and the apparent resistivity becomes

$$\rho_a = \frac{\pi \Delta V}{4IMN} (AB - MN)(AB + MN)$$

When $AB \gg MN$

$$AB \pm MN \approx AB$$

so the usual approximation is

$$\rho_a \approx \frac{\pi E}{I} \left(\frac{AB}{2} \right)^2$$

where $E \approx \Delta V/MN$. The physical meaning is simple. Increasing $AB/2$ spreads current farther from the source electrodes, so the experiment samples a larger and deeper volume of Earth. A sounding therefore plots ρ_a against $AB/2$ on logarithmic axes because both spacing and resistivity vary over orders of magnitude, and because the experiment is most sensitive to structure whose size is comparable to its burial depth.

The Schlumberger sounding assumes the subsurface is locally 1D, so lateral variations must be weak over the scale of the array. Electrode effects matter because the measured potential is controlled by the immediate electrical environment of the current and especially the potential electrodes. When the MN spacing changes, branch segments can shift vertically on a log-log sounding plot. That vertical shift is multiplicative in apparent resistivity, so the standard correction is a constant scaling of the smaller- MN branch until the overlap matches the larger- MN branch.

Figure 1: Schlumberger sounding geometry. The sounding center stays fixed while $AB/2$ grows. The potential dipole is kept short compared with the current electrode spacing.

3 Data reduction

3.1 Raw branches and electrode-spacing correction

The raw sounding contains two branches: a shallow branch measured with $MN/2 = 0.1$ m and a larger-spacing branch measured with $MN/2 = 1.0$ m. Figure 2 shows the raw data on log-log axes. The two

branches overlap at

$$AB/2 = 6 \text{ m} \quad \text{and} \quad AB/2 = 10 \text{ m}$$

The offset is small but systematic. Taking the larger potential spacing to be more reliable, the branch ratios are

$$c_6 = \frac{3.22}{2.83} = 1.1378$$

$$c_{10} = \frac{4.47}{3.91} = 1.1432$$

A multiplicative correction belongs in log space, so the constant factor was taken as the geometric mean of the two overlap ratios

$$c = 10^{\frac{1}{2}[\log_{10}(c_6) + \log_{10}(c_{10})]} = 1.1405$$

The corrected small- MN branch is therefore

$$\rho_{a,\text{corr}} = c \rho_{a, MN/2=0.1}$$

After applying this factor the overlap points become

$$\rho_{a,\text{corr}}(6 \text{ m}) = 3.2277 \text{ } \Omega\text{m}$$

$$\rho_{a,\text{corr}}(10 \text{ m}) = 4.4594 \text{ } \Omega\text{m}$$

which agree with the trusted $MN/2 = 1.0 \text{ m}$ branch to within about 0.24%. Figure 3 shows the corrected sounding.

Figure 2: Raw 2026 Schlumberger sounding. The two $MN/2$ branches are offset slightly in the overlap region. The dashed line marks the 50 m cutoff. The 75 m point is displayed but not interpreted as geology.

Figure 3: Corrected sounding after multiplying the $MN/2 = 0.1$ m branch by $c = 1.1405$. The corrected small- MN branch now overlays the trusted $MN/2 = 1.0$ m branch at 6 and 10 m.

3.2 Rejected far-offset data and fit set

The data past 50 m are affected by the pier and sea wall and that the jump at 75 m is not geologic. I therefore retained the 50 m value but rejected the 75 m point from the inversion. The Q column was preserved in the processed tables, but its meaning is not documented, so it was not assigned an independent physical interpretation and it was not used to weight the inversion. The 50 m point does have $Q = 3$ and it later carries the largest residual, so the deepest part of the final model is treated as approximate rather than exact.

To avoid double counting at the overlap spacings, the corrected $MN/2 = 0.1$ m points at 6 and 10 m were kept for branch comparison only, while the inversion used the more trusted $MN/2 = 1.0$ m values at those spacings. The final fit set therefore contains 11 corrected apparent resistivities from

$$0.3 \leq AB/2 \leq 50 \text{ m}$$

4 Occam inversion and forward modeling

The MATLAB function `SFit.m` computes Schlumberger apparent resistivity for a layered Earth using a 19-point Ghosh fast Hankel transform filter and a Koefoed resistivity transform recursion. From the course notes, the continuous forward problem is

$$\rho_a(AB) = \left(\frac{AB}{2}\right)^2 \int_0^\infty T_1(\lambda) J_1\left(\frac{AB}{2}\lambda\right) \lambda d\lambda$$

with layer recursion

$$T_i(\lambda) = \frac{T_{i+1} + \rho_i \tanh(\lambda t_i)}{1 + T_{i+1} \tanh(\lambda t_i) / \rho_i}$$

The recursion starts from the bottom half-space,

$$T_N = \rho_N$$

and works upward to the surface.

4.1 Occam parameterization and objective function

The inversion is carried out in log-resistivity using a fixed 20-layer mesh. The model vector is

$$\mathbf{m} = [\log_{10} \rho_1, \log_{10} \rho_2, \dots, \log_{10} \rho_{20}]^T$$

with fixed layer thicknesses

$$t_j = 0.1 \times 1.3^{j-1} \text{ m} \quad j = 1, \dots, 19$$

so the finite part of the mesh is 48.3973 m thick and the twentieth layer is a half-space. Only resistivities are inverted for. Thicknesses remain fixed throughout.

The data and forward response are both defined in log space

$$\mathbf{d} = \log_{10}(\rho_a^{obs})$$

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{m}) = \log_{10}(\rho_a^{pred})$$

The Occam functional is

$$U(\mathbf{m}) = \|W[\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{m})]\|^2 + \mu \|R\mathbf{m}\|^2$$

where R is the first-difference roughness operator. Linearizing about the current model gives

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{m} + \Delta\mathbf{m}) \approx \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{m}) + J\Delta\mathbf{m}$$

and the regularized Gauss-Newton step used here is

$$\mathbf{m}_{k+1} = [\mu R^T R + (WJ)^T WJ]^{-1} (WJ)^T W [\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{m}_k) + J\mathbf{m}_k]$$

The Jacobian J was computed by central finite differences. Because the file does not include documented measurement uncertainties and because Q is undefined, a uniform error floor of

$$\sigma_{\log} = 0.0200$$

was assigned to every log-apparent-resistivity datum. That corresponds to about 4.7129% relative error and only sets the scale of the Occam target misfit. The starting model was a homogeneous half-space with resistivity equal to the median corrected datum

$$\rho_0 = 2.4521 \text{ } \Omega\text{m}$$

A sampled line search in μ was carried out at each iteration, and whenever the sampled curve bracketed the target

$$\chi_*^2 \approx M = 11$$

a bisection solve in $\log_{10} \mu$ was used to recover the target-crossing value rather than simply taking the nearest sampled grid point. The first iteration could not reach the target, so the minimum-misfit model occurred at

$$\mu_1 = 46.4159$$

By the second iteration the trade-off curve crossed $\text{RMS} = 1$ at

$$\mu_2 = 972.6773$$

Figure 4: Second-iteration Occam line search. The chosen μ is the target-crossing value found by bisection between the sampled grid points that bracket $\text{RMS} = 1$.

The third and fourth iterations gave

$$\mu_3 = 987.8090 \quad \mu_4 = 987.5057$$

so both the trade-off parameter and the model stabilized by the fourth iteration. The final accepted model used

$$\mu = 987.5057$$

and gave

$$\chi^2 = 11.0000$$

$$\text{RMS} = 1.0000$$

so the model is the smoothest one found that fits the accepted data at the required level. Table 1 summarizes the inversion settings.

Table 1: Occam inversion settings and fit summary

Quantity	Value
Data used in inversion	11 corrected points
Model parameterization	20 layers, resistivity only
Thickness law	$t_j = 0.1 \times 1.3^{j-1}$ m
Finite model thickness	48.3973 m
Starting half-space resistivity	2.4521 Ωm
Log-space error floor	0.0200
Second-iteration target-crossing μ	972.6773
Final trade-off parameter	987.5057
Final χ^2	11.0
Final normalized RMS	1.0

Figures 5, 6, and 7 show the final data fit, the recovered layered model, and the residuals. The log-residual RMS is 0.0200 decades and the mean absolute relative error is 3.7766%.

Figure 5: Final data-model comparison. Filled circles are the 11 corrected data used in the Occam inversion. Open squares are corrected overlap points shown for reference but not double-counted. The 75 m point is shown separately and was rejected.

Figure 6: Recovered 20-layer Occam model. Resistivity increases smoothly with depth from about 1 Ωm near the surface to about 16 Ωm in the deepest half-space.

Figure 7: Log-space residuals for the accepted data. The deepest 50 m point has the largest absolute residual, so the deepest part of the model should be treated as approximate.

5 Interpretation

5.1 Resistivity structure, local 1D validity, and non-uniqueness

The recovered model increases monotonically from

$$\rho_{\text{top}} = 1.0009 \, \Omega\text{m} \approx 1.0 \, \Omega\text{m}$$

to

$$\rho_{\text{bottom}} = 16.0746 \, \Omega\text{m} \approx 16.1 \, \Omega\text{m}$$

The transition is gradual. The model reaches about $10 \, \Omega\text{m}$ near 8–10 m depth and continues to increase slowly below that. So the sounding is not well represented by a sharp two-layer contact even though the apparent resistivity curve looks superficially two-layer. The geologically sensible picture is seawater-saturated unconsolidated beach sand over a more resistive sandstone or bedrock sandstone whose bulk resistivity rises with consolidation and lower effective porosity.

The accepted part of the data is compatible with a local 1D interpretation because the corrected curve is smooth and monotonic from 0.3 to 50 m, with no abrupt reversals after the branch shift is removed. The 75 m point violates that behavior and is therefore best understood as external contamination from the pier and sea wall rather than a genuine subsurface layer.

The final model is not unique. Resistivity sounding always suffers from equivalence and suppression, and both matter here because a gradual increase with depth tends to smear out the middle of the section. What is well constrained is the overall upward trend,

$$\rho(z) \uparrow \text{ with depth}$$

together with the shallow and deep end-member resistivities. What is only approximate is the exact depth range over which the intermediate increase occurs.

5.2 Porosity estimates from Archie's law

Using the course form of Archie's law with seawater resistivity

$$\rho_w = 0.25 \, \Omega\text{m}$$

and exponent

$$a = 2$$

the rock resistivity is

$$\rho_r = \rho_w \phi^{-2}$$

so the porosity is

$$\phi = \sqrt{\frac{\rho_w}{\rho_r}}$$

Using the shallow and deep end members of the Occam model,

$$\phi_{\text{top}} = \sqrt{\frac{0.25}{1.0009}} = 0.4998 \approx 0.5, \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_{\text{bottom}} = \sqrt{\frac{0.25}{16.0746}} = 0.1247$$

These values make geologic sense. A porosity of about 0.50 is entirely plausible for loose, water-saturated beach sand. A porosity of about 0.12 is also plausible for sandstone or weathered bedrock sandstone if it retains some connected pore space and fractures. The numbers should not be read too literally because the Archie exponent and the assumption of full seawater saturation are both idealizations, but the contrast is physically reasonable.

Table 2: Archie porosity estimates from the end-member resistivities of the Occam model

Interpreted unit	Resistivity (Ωm)	Porosity	Interpretation
Near-surface beach sand	$1.0009 \approx 1.0$	$0.4998 \approx 0.5$	Loose seawater-saturated sand
Deep sandstone / bedrock	$16.0746 \approx 16.1$	0.1247	Consolidated sandstone or fractured bedrock

6 Conclusions

The 2026 Scripps Beach resistivity sounding is a Schlumberger 1D sounding with a small but systematic branch offset caused by changing the potential electrode spacing. Multiplying the $MN/2 = 0.1$ m branch by

$$c = 1.1405$$

removes that offset and produces a single corrected sounding curve. The 75 m point is rejected because it lies beyond the 50 m cutoff identified in the reduction handout and is consistent with pier / sea wall contamination rather than geology.

The accepted 11-point data set is fit with `SFit.m` and a 20-layer Occam inversion in log-resistivity. The line search is solved to the target crossing rather than by keeping the nearest sampled μ , so every downstream quantity uses the refined trade-off parameter. The final smooth model fits the corrected data at

$$\chi^2 = 11.0 \quad \text{RMS} = 1.0$$

and recovers a resistivity increase from about 1 Ωm at the surface to about 16 Ωm at depth. Therefore the sounding is best interpreted as seawater-saturated unconsolidated sand over more resistive sandstone or bedrock sandstone, with the increase in resistivity spread over depth rather than concentrated at one sharp interface.

Applying Archie's law with $a = 2$ and $\rho_w = 0.25 \Omega\text{m}$ gives

$$\phi_{\text{top}} = 0.4998 \approx 0.5 \quad \phi_{\text{bottom}} = 0.1247$$

which are geologically plausible for beach sand and sandstone respectively.

References

- [1] S. Constable, Resistivity data reduction handout, SIO 182 course material
- [2] S. Constable, Electrical Methods, SIO 182 notes, April 25, 2022
- [3] S. Constable, Geophysical Inversion, SIO 182 notes
- [4] S. Constable, Electromagnetic Induction and the Magnetotelluric Method, SIO 182 notes